

Original Research Article

Planning in Clinical Supervision and the Professional Development of Student Teachers in Higher Technical Training Colleges in Cameroon

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Abstract

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This study aims at investigating effects of planning for supervision and its impact on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. It is based on the problem of inadequate clinical supervision model of planning which has negative impacts on the professional development of student teachers. The main objective was to ascertain how clinical supervision influences professional development of student teachers in higher technical training colleges in Cameroon. Based on this, research questions were formed and hypotheses generated. The scope was limited to student-teachers and supervisors in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The sample population was 346 student teachers and 08 supervisors. The Elizabeth Holloway's System model (1995), was used as theoretical backup of the study. The study made use of the sequential explanatory design and used the purposive sampling for selecting the schools and the classes for the study. It also made use of the inferential and descriptive statistics. The instruments for data collection were the questionnaire for student-teachers, interview for the supervisors and cooperating teachers and observation guides. The questionnaires were made up of items about planning for supervision. The supervisors were equally interviewed on this. From the results we have the following conclusions: 81.1% of supervisors do not carry out planning for supervision with their supervisees. This means that there is a significant impact on planning for supervision on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The study recommends that supervision schools be opened to train supervisors.

Keywords: Clinical Supervision, Professional development, Teaching practice

INTRODUCTION

Observations made over the years indicate that a large proportion of graduate student teachers entering into the teaching profession in Cameroon secondary schools lack adequate teaching skills that are necessary drivers to their professional development. (Titanji and Nchaih, 2010). The acquisition of appropriate skills makes teachers to be effective and effective in terms of learning outcome. This is to say, that if the professional skills of

teachers are not developed or are found wanting, then there is a problem because quality education cannot be attained without the provision of quality teachers. At the beginning of their career and all through, teachers should be assisted to develop teaching skills thereby allowing them to grow professionally.

These skills are acquired through a number of ways including teaching practice, seminars and workshops for

teachers. The government, attempt towards the provision of quality teachers has opened curriculum training schools to facilitate the professional training and development of teachers and student-teachers. Some of the schools are Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges (ENSET) in Kumba and Bamenda, Government Technical Teacher Training College (ENIET) Kumba, to name a few. Students' achievement is closely linked to teachers' input (Sergiovanni and Starratt, 2007). One way to ensure that teachers are providing effective instruction is to implement effective supervision. Regrettably, supervision has been equated to inspection, an administrative task that has to be achieved by an authority referred to as "inspector" whose job is to evaluate and control teachers' performance. (Sergiovanni and Starratt, 2007). The flawed nature and process of exercise often result to inadequate preparation by teachers and ineffective curriculum implementation. Considering that supervision of instruction involves the process of planning, class observation and feedback, this therefore study investigates the influence of Planning on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. It hypothesizes that there is no significant relationship between the impact of Planning and the professional development of Student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon.

Teaching Practice

It is a professional exercise which is focused on helping the student-teacher to bridge the gap between theory and practice in education and develop competence as well. In the process of bridging the gap between educational theories and practice, the student-teacher, through a program of cooperative and interactive guidance, acquires valuable skills in teaching and the management of teaching from experienced teachers thus improving their quality (Endeley, 2014). According to Robbins and Alvy (2004), teaching practice is used to improve student learning through supervision and professional development. Academic supervision is conducted to find out the teacher's potential in carrying out learning activities ranging from planning, implementation, and assessment activities.

Higher Technical teacher training colleges in Cameroon teacher have always provided opportunities for prospective teachers to practice teaching in school settings while still in their preparation programs. Since its creation, these experiences has occurred during the last year of the preparation program and lasted approximately six to eight weeks, which is the whole of second term. In many programs, this was the only experience that prospective teachers had in a school or with students. The typical experience included assigning the student teacher to an experienced teacher in the school who

would provide guidance and supervision. The supervisor would provide a minimum of four visits to observe the prospective teacher teach. (Endeley, 2014).

Clinical supervision

Historical data holds that supervision was carried out at the beginning of its development using an inspection approach where by supervisors came to school, planned with their supervisees before they went to class and observed them teaching (Poole 2012). Supervision of instruction only involved the two parties where the focus of the supervisor's attention was to find errors based on standard work that was formulated by the education authority. The teacher carried out the task in accordance with standard operational procedures. The supervision approach moved in a more democratic direction; supervisors and teachers could exchange opinions about improving the quality of learning. The development of supervision today emphasizes more on the efforts of teachers to develop the quality of learning through continuous professional development. This approach is known as clinical Supervision.

Clinical supervision of teachers is a concept born in the 1960s at Harvard by Morris Cogan (1961), and continued later on at the University of Pittsburgh. It originated in the frustration that Morris Cogan and Robert Goldhammer (1961) felt while trying to improve the instructional practices of beginning teachers. By this approach of planning, observing, analysing and having post conferences with students, future teachers were engaged in the practice of enquiry wherein every event was subject to examination. The process was, then, named "clinical supervision" because it operated right in the clinic of the classroom wherein every act was observed and discussed. (Goldhammer and Cogan, 1961). Pajak,(2003) describes clinical supervision as a process that involves a conference with the student-teacher to preview objectives and the lesson plans; direct observation of the lesson; and a follow-up conference with the student, with feedback on strengths and areas of improvement. The three stages in clinical supervision consist of Planning for supervision, Class observation and Feedback conference. (Olivia and Pawlas, 2004)

The planning stage in Clinical Supervision

At the Planning stage, also considered by others as Pre - observation Conference (Aydan,2000),the task of the student teacher is to mentally rehearse and orally describe the upcoming lesson, including the purpose and the content, what the teacher will do, and what students are expected to do and learn. While the clinical supervisor's task is to learn about and understand what the student teacher has in mind for the lesson to be

taught by asking probing and clarifying questions as well as giving hints on how to go about the lesson. Together, the teacher and the supervisor meet and decide about data collection strategies as regards to the teacher's and students' behaviour with a focus on the area to be observed. For example, the teacher might request the supervisor to focus on the way he / she uses the board or on the way he/ she ask questions. In this way, the supervisor is well aware of the teacher's lesson plan, objectives and areas that need to be addressed prior to getting in class.

Holloway, (1995) in her theoretical system approach to supervision opines that the heart of supervision is the alliance created in the relationship between supervisor and supervisee which is mutually involving and aimed at bestowing power to both members. The relationship creates the holding environment for the supervisee's reflection on and growth as a developing professional. Ideally, supervision is a growth-enhancing relationship adhering to the principles of positive psychology and relational cultural theory. Not only does this create a condition for learning, but it also models relational and interpersonal qualities that are a necessary quality of a therapeutic relationship. Supervisees have the opportunity to learn by experiencing and reflecting on their interpersonal behaviour and emotional reactions to being in a fully engaged learning environment. In the model, there are three essential elements that guide the understanding of the formation and quality of the relationship: (a) the interpersonal structure of the relationship as described by the power and engagement across the five sub roles of supervision, (b) the developmental phase of relationship, and (c) the learning contract of supervision (Holloway, 1995)

Hoover et al, (2011) says that before the supervisor leaves the teacher's classroom it is important to wrap up the pre-conference by reviewing the teacher's lesson in simple terms. Summarize everything that the teacher has included and have him or her correct any errors in the understanding of their lesson and instructional design. Allowing the teacher to submit additional evidence such as lesson plans, student work and anecdotal records will also add to the teacher's ownership of the observational data and the process of supervision (Nolan & Hoover, 2011) for teacher growth. Thus, pre conferencing provides the student teacher the opportunity to do a proper presentation of his or her work. This enhances professional growth.

Professional Development

Fullan (2006) states that professional development involves workshops, programs and related activities that are designed to enable teachers acquire new ideas, skills and competences necessary for improvement in the classroom. He further gave five points which represent a

clarion call to radically change our concept to what teacher learning should entail; firstly, that professional development is a major obstacle to progress in teacher learning. Again, he supported Elmore's observation in that teachers need to learn to do the right thing in the setting where they work. Thirdly he stated that student learning pends on every teacher learning all the time. The fourth observation is that the first three components depend on deprivatizing teaching as teachers work together to continuously improve instruction. The last component is that teachers working conditions are inimical to the four previous points.

In this study professional development is a combination of tools, strategies, resources and training sessions for educators (student teachers) to improve their teaching quality and effectiveness. These resources allow teachers to further their knowledge in their subject areas and allows for mentorship and the opportunity to learn new teaching techniques.

METHODOLOGY

Cameroon has ten higher technical teacher training colleges distributed in all the ten regions of the country. This study was conducted in four Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges chosen from four out of the ten regions. These include; the South, Littoral, North West and South West Regions Cameroon. The sequential explanatory design was adopted for this study.

The study employed the purposive sampling technique in choosing the schools and the final year student – teachers and teachers of HTTTC Bambili, Kumba, Douala ad Ebolowa because they were the ones on teaching practice at the time of the study. The sample consisted of 346 student teachers from the technical teacher training colleges and 08 teachers / supervisors taken from the four regions of Cameroon. Table 1

Instruments for Data Collection

A triangulation of close ended questionnaires, the interview and observation guide were used for the study. The questionnaire designed for the student teachers, while an interview guide for supervisors. An observation checklist was also used. The questionnaire was useful in obtaining objective data without participants being manipulated by the researcher. Thus, the participants in this study had freedom to express their opinions and make suggestions. The questionnaire used for the study was made up of two parts, that is part one and part two. Part one contained items on respondents' personal characteristics such as sex, name of institution, Department. Part two contained items pertaining to the variable of the study that is, planning for supervision. Reliability and validity were assured because the

Table 1. Sample of Study

Region	Selected schools	Population of students		Population of teachers	
		Gender		Gender	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
North west	ENSET Bambili	40	30	1	1
South west	ENSET Kumba	40	55	1	1
Littoral	ENSET Douala	41	65	1	1
South	ENSET Ebolowa	35	40	1	1
Total		156	190	04	04

Source: Field Survey. ENSET Kumba, Bambili, Ebolowa , Douala,2022

supervisors and other experts checked the instruments and items.

Analysis of quantitative data

The data collected from the field was first processed using EPIData 3.1 whereby, all the participants' responses were keyed, in accordance with each of the test items. The Pearson test was used to test the hypotheses. The Chi-Square test was used to statistically compare the practice of planning for supervision by the four training institutions. With the use of a Chi-Square test, one could detect if all four training colleges carry out clinical supervision in almost the same manner or vary greatly in their practices.

FINDINGS

Findings on the objective of the study which set out to investigate the impact of planning on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon are reported in the following paragraphs as presented on tables and pie charts. Table 2, Figure 1

In aggregate, only 18.9% of student teachers with a mean of 1.57 below the cutoff point of 2.5 agreed that their supervisor carried out planning before supervision of instructions whereas majority of the students 81.1% disagreed. Specifically, while 23.0% (79) of student teachers agreed that their supervisor met with them before teaching practice, majority 77.0% (265) disagreed. Also, while 20.9% (72) of student teachers indicated that their supervisors asked for lesson objectives, majority of them 79.1% (272) disagreed. Similarly, only 20.1% (69) of student teachers opined that a cordial relationship existed between them and supervisors while 79.9% (275) denied. Findings also showed that only 19.8% (68) of student teachers agreed that their supervisors told them what is expected during teaching practices whereas 80.2% (276) disagreed. In the same trend, only 18.6% (64) of student teachers accepted to have discussion with

supervisor before teaching practices whereas majority 81.4% (280) do not.

In the same weight, only 16.9% (58) of student teachers accepted that their supervisor asked about the teaching-learning methods and instructional materials to be used while a majority 83.1% (286) disagreed. Furthermore, only 16.9% (58) of student teachers 16.9% (58) agreed that their supervisor check their lesson plans before taking it to class while a majority of them 83.1% (286) denied. Finally, only 17.4% (60) of student teachers agreed that there is degree of guidance before teaching practice while a majority of them 83.6% (284) disagreed. Table 3

In line with the student teachers own opinion, observation carried out by the researcher revealed that many supervisors did not carry out planning of supervision with student teachers before teaching practice as indicated with a relatively low mean value ranging from 1.37 to 1.71 below the cutoff point of 2.5. To be explicit, it was observed that many supervisors did not very often meet and discuss with their supervisees before teaching practice, guide student-teacher on the selection of instructional materials and how to prepare an effective lesson, corrects lesson plans before student teacher takes to class and ensures that all instructional materials are ok before student teacher goes to teach.

Again, it was observed that many supervisors did not very often make it easier for student teachers to meet them. Statistics showed that the calculated r-value is 0.741^{**} six times higher than the critical value of 0.105 at df of 349. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative retained. In other words, planning of instructional supervision has a significant, positive and strong impact on professional development of student teachers. The positivity of the correlation value implies that professional development of student teachers is more likely to increase when supervisors adequately carry out planning of instructional supervision and this strong impact on professional development of student teachers is also support with a high explanatory power of 78.5%. Table 4

Based on the eight supervisors sampled opinion in relation to planning, some of them said they often met

Table 2. Student Teachers Opinion on Planning of Supervision before Teaching Practice

Statements	Stretched				Collapsed		Mean	Std. Dev
	SA	A	D	SD	SA/A	D/SD		
Your supervisor meets with you before teaching practice.	19 (5.5%)	60 (17.4%)	162 (47.1%)	103 (29.9%)	79 (23.0%)	265 (77.0%)	1.99	.835
Your supervisor discusses with you before teaching practice.	8 (2.3%)	56 (16.3%)	159 (46.2%)	121 (35.2%)	64 (18.6%)	280 (81.4%)	1.86	.767
He/she tells you what is expected of you during teaching practice.	11 (3.2%)	57 (16.6%)	171 (49.7%)	105 (30.5%)	68 (19.8%)	276 (80.2%)	1.92	.771
Your supervisor asks about your lesson's objectives.	6 (1.7%)	66 (19.2%)	149 (43.3%)	123 (35.8%)	72 (20.9%)	272 (79.1%)	1.87	.777
He/she asks about the teaching learning methods you intend to use.	9 (2.6%)	49 (14.2%)	164 (47.7%)	122 (35.5%)	58 (16.9%)	286 (83.1%)	1.84	.760
He/she asks about the instructional materials.	10 (2.9%)	48 (14.0%)	140 (40.7%)	146 (42.4%)	58 (16.9%)	286 (83.1%)	1.77	.794
Your supervisor correct your lesson plans before you take them to class.	13 (3.8%)	45 (13.1%)	147 (42.7%)	139 (40.4%)	58 (16.9%)	286 (83.1%)	1.80	.806
There is a cordial relationship between you and your supervisor.	12 (3.5%)	57 (16.6%)	145 (42.2%)	130 (37.8%)	69 (20.1%)	275 (79.9%)	1.86	.815
There is a degree of guidance before teaching practice.	12 (3.5%)	48 (14.0%)	156 (45.3%)	128 (37.2%)	60 (17.4%)	284 (83.6%)	1.85	.808
There is a warm climate during planning.	5 (1.5%)	58 (16.9%)	143 (41.6%)	138 (40.1%)	63 (18.3%)	281 (81.7%)	1.80	.767
Multiple Responses Set (MRS)	105 (3.1%)	544 (15.8%)	1537 (44.7%)	1254 (36.5%)	649 (18.9%)	2791 (81.1%)	1.57	.79

Figure 1. Student Teachers Opinion on Planning of Supervision before Teaching Practice**Table 3.** Observation by Researcher on Planning

Items	Very often	Often	Not very often	Never	Mean	Std. Deviation
Meet and discuss with your supervisee before teaching practice.	0	6	8	14	1.71	.810
Guides student-teacher on the selection of instructional materials.	1	0	14	13	1.57	.573
Guides student teacher on how to prepare an effective lesson.	0	1	13	13	1.56	.577
Corrects lesson plans before student teacher takes to class.	0	0	14	14	1.50	.509
Ensures that all instructional materials are ok before student teacher goes to teach.	0	0	10	17	1.37	.492
Ensures that student teacher teaches with a lesson plan.	0	2	9	17	1.46	.637
Student teacher can always have access to you.	0	0	10	17	1.43	.573

No of observations 28

Table 4. Supervisors Opinion on Issues Related to Planning with Supervisees before Teaching Practice

Questions	Themes	Quotations
Do you usually meet with your supervisees before teaching practice?	Yes	“Yes, I meet with the supervisees” “Always”. “Yes”.
	Not often	“Not often” “Sometimes”
Do you discuss with them about how the process is going to be like and what is expected of them?	Always	“Always” “Yes” “Definitely”.
Do you correct their lesson plans before they take them to class?	Always	“Always”. “Sure” “Yes”

with their supervisees before teaching practice while some said they did not usually meet with their supervisees before teaching practice. Again, all eight supervisors also indicated that they discussed with their supervisee about the process of teaching of teaching practice and what was expected of them. Finally, all eight supervisors also said they corrected their supervisee lesson plans before they took to class. However, despite the supervisor’s claims to carry out planning for teaching practice with their supervisees, findings from the student teachers and observation carried out indicated that many supervisors did not carry out planning for teaching practice with their supervisees before teaching practice.

Professional Development of Student Teachers

In aggregate, based on professional development, only 26.1% of student teachers with mean of 1.98 on a scale of 1-4 used appropriate instructional pedagogy approaches while majority 73.9% did not. Specifically, 24.0% (82) of student teachers agreed to use appropriate instructional material whereas majority 76.0% (259) disagreed. Also, 22.8% (78) of student teachers agreed to set instructional objectives that will adequately measure what students are to learn while 77.2% (264) disagreed. Furthermore, while 22.5% (77) of student teachers were able to use different teaching method based on the subject matter, majority 77.5% (265) did not. Similarly, 21.6% (74) of student teachers aligned assessment to the objective and method of teaching while a majority of them 78.4% (268) did not. Also, 20.5% (70) of student teachers agreed to use various approaches in classroom management to provide a conducive environment for learning while many of them 79.5% (272) did not. Table 5, Figure 2

Furthermore only 19.9% (68) of student teachers accepted to evaluate students based on what they know while many 80.1% (274) did not. Again, only 24.3% (83) of student teachers agreed to employ various leadership styles in the classroom depending on the situation or the

context while 75.7% (259) disagreed. Similarly, only 26.3% (90) of student teachers agreed to provide expert support to learners while 73.7% (252) disagreed. Again, only 21.6% (74) of student teachers agreed to have problem solving skills with 78.4% (268) do not. Finally, on a positive note, more of student teachers 57.9% (198) agreed to have a positive attitude towards learners while 42.15 (144) disagreed. Table 6

Furthermore, in accordance with the student teachers own opinion, observation carried showed that professional development of student teachers was low as indicated with a relatively low mean for all attributes ranging from 1.14 to 1.61 below the cutoff point of 2.5. Explicitly, many of the student teachers did not often use appropriate instructional materials. Also, many of the student teachers did not very often set objectives that accurately measures what students learn. Furthermore, many student teachers did not very often make use of different teaching methods. In like manner, many student teachers did not very often use various approaches in classroom management. Again, many student teachers did not very often evaluate students based on what they knew. Finally, many student teachers did not very often have positive attitude toward learners and content mastery.

Verification of Hypothesis One

Ho1: there is no significant relationship between the impact of Planning and the professional development of Student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon.

Ha1: there is a significant relationship between the impact of planning and the development of Student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in the South West and North West Regions Cameroon.

Score of the independent variable (planning) was aggregated from 10 items and that for dependent variable (professional development of student teachers) was

Table 5. Professional Development of Student Teachers

Statements	Stretched				Collapsed		Mean	Std. Dev
	SA	A	D	SD	SA/A	D/SD		
I use appropriate instructional materials	11 (3.2%)	71 (20.8%)	142 (41.6%)	117 (34.3%)	82 (24.0%)	259 (76.0%)	1.93	.823
I set instructional objectives that will adequately measure what students are to learn.	16 (4.7%)	62 (18.1%)	153 (44.7%)	111 (32.5%)	78 (22.8%)	264 (77.2%)	1.95	.832
I am able to use different teaching methods based on the subject matter.	13 (3.8%)	64 (18.7%)	152 (44.4%)	113 (33.0%)	77 (22.5%)	265 (77.5%)	1.93	.817
I align my assessment to the objectives and methods of teaching.	13 (3.8%)	61 (17.8%)	154 (42.4%)	123 (36.0%)	74 (21.6%)	268 (78.4%)	1.89	.825
I use various approaches in classroom management to provide a conducive environment for learning.	6 (1.8%)	64 (18.7%)	159 (46.5%)	113 (33.0%)	70 (20.5%)	272 (79.5%)	1.89	.760
I evaluate students based on what they have learnt.	14 (4.1%)	54 (15.8%)	141 (41.2%)	133 (38.9%)	68 (19.9%)	274 (80.1%)	1.85	.831
I employ various leadership styles in the classroom depending on the situation or the context.	13 (3.8%)	70 (20.5%)	136 (39.8%)	123 (36.0%)	83 (24.3%)	259 (75.7%)	1.92	.844
I have a positive attitude towards my learners.	108 (31.6%)	90 (26.3%)	88 (25.7%)	56 (16.4%)	198 (57.9%)	144 (42.1%)	2.73	1.077
I provide expert support to my learners.	29 (8.5%)	61 (17.8%)	112 (32.7%)	140 (40.9%)	90 (26.3%)	252 (73.7%)	1.94	.962
I have skills in problem solving	12 (3.5%)	62 (18.1%)	104 (30.4%)	164 (48.0%)	74 (21.6%)	268 (78.4%)	1.77	.867
Multiple Responses Set (MRS)	235 (6.9%)	659 (19.3%)	1332 (39.0%)	1193 (34.9%)	894 (26.1%)	2525 (73.9%)	1.98	.864

Figure 2. Professional Development of Student Teachers**Table 6.** Observation by Researcher on Student Teachers Professional Development

Items	Very often	Often	Not very often	Never	Mean	Std. Deviation
Uses appropriate instructional materials.	0	1	15	12	1.61	.567
Set objectives that accurately measure what students learn.	0	0	9	19	1.32	.476
Use of different teaching methods.	0	3	7	18	1.46	.693
Use of various approaches in classroom management.	0	0	6	22	1.21	.418
Evaluating students based on what they have learnt.	0	0	7	21	1.25	.441
Positive attitude towards learners.	0	0	9	19	1.32	.476
Mastery of content.	0	0	4	24	1.14	.356

No of observations 28

Table 7. Relationship between Planning and Professional Development of Student Teachers

Pearson test	Planning	Professional Development of student teachers	Explanatory power of relationship in terms of % (Nagelkerke)
Planning	R-value	1	.741**
	p-value		.000
	N	344	341
Professional Development	R-value	.741**	1
	p-value	.000	
	N	341	341
			.785 (78.5%)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
At 0.05 cl and df=339, r-critical value is 0.105

computed from 10 items. The results are presented on the Table 7 above

Statistics showed that the calculated r-value is 0.741** was six times higher than the critical value of 0.105 at df of 349. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative retained. In other words, planning for clinical supervision has a significant positive and strong impact on professional development of student teachers. The positivity of the correlation value implies that the professional development of student teachers is more likely to increase when supervisors adequately carry out planning of instructional supervision and this strong impact on the professional development of student teachers is also supported with a high explanatory power of 78.5%.

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the student teachers own opinion, observation carried out by the researcher revealed that many supervisors do not carry out planning of supervision with student teachers before teaching practice as indicated with a relatively low mean value ranging from. Though the supervisors said they carried out planning of teaching practice with their supervisees, findings from the study however indicates that professional development of student teachers is more likely to increase when supervisors adequately carry out planning of instructional supervision with a consequent strong impact on professional development of student teachers. Thus, supervision is the backbone towards determining the effectiveness of a school (Glickman et al., 1995).

Furthermore, the findings also sits well with the review by Jorissen (2006). She stated that the pre-observation conference (planning stage) is the place where the supervisor sits with the teacher and helps the teacher clarify the logistics of the lesson.

Jorissen stated that: *“Pre-observation conference fosters dialogue and communication, reduces the teacher’s anxiety, and gives the teacher a chance to conceptually rehearse the lesson”* (p. 24).

This opportunity should be more of a reflective one as the teacher walks through the plan and assesses whether there is “clear flow”. Moreover she goes on to state that this opportunity, “gives the supervisor or principal a sense of how the teacher sees the impending lesson in the context of instructional objectives.” It goes without saying that this will help improve on the professional development of student teachers in Cameroon. Elmore (2004), stated that professional development can provide networking opportunities. Many professional development opportunities such as teaching practice, workshops, conferences, and others allow teachers to branch out and meet other pedagogues within their industry who may be able to help them with career opportunities in the future. When you decide you want a change or are ready to move up in your teaching career, your professional network and the professional relationships you forged will come in handy.

To add, Professional development and continuing education and learning opportunities are great ways to stay up-to-date on industry knowledge and trends. Education is constantly evolving, so teachers should use professional development and training opportunities to expand their knowledge base, learn new practices and techniques, and embrace new technology (Elmore, 2004).

Furthermore, (Moss and Brookhart 2009,) opined that planning for teaching practice is very important because the second aspect of a pre-observation is to discuss what instructional strategies will be used. Instructional strategies are the different approaches that a teacher might take to achieve the learning targets for the class. Instructional strategies should activate students’ prior knowledge, engaged them in learning, keep them on task and foster their critical thinking skills. Instructional strategies are one of the elements of effective pedagogy and should be centred on the particular needs of students in the classroom. They further stated that the third aspect of the pre-observation conference is the discussion around assessment of learning. During this time the discussion is centred what form of assessment will be used to check for student’s understanding of content and learning.

Similarly, Radi (2007) in his study suggested that there should be a discussion session between supervisor and teachers and the teachers to receive the feedback of the supervision outcomes. From these discussions, supervisors may enlighten the teachers about their weaknesses and strengths regarding techniques, methods, approaches and teaching aids used. In addition to this, study by Haliza (2005) & Baharom (2002), found that clinical supervision has not been administered adequately.

It is clear from their observations that without planning for teaching practice, the student teachers may not be able to properly state objectives, carry out proper questioning techniques, measure students based on what they know, have a positive attitude towards their learners and as such cannot grow professionally. A good supervision involves activities that aids, directs and informs teachers of what should be done or have been done and not merely finding faults in the teachers' teaching. Baharom (2002) in his study found out that Clinical supervision has failed to increase teachers' integrity and has not helped to motivate teachers to become innovative nor to have more initiative (Glanz et al., 2005). This finding by Glanz et al is the basis why supervisors need to take their jobs seriously to enable student teachers develop professionally.

Conclusively, it is evident that most supervisors do not plan with their supervisees before teaching practice. Also this has a negative impact on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. Therefore while the study recommends, that the government should open more supervision schools where supervisors will be properly trained on how to go about supervision so that they can effectively carry out their tasks and help student teachers grow professionally and that constant follow up should be done to ensure that supervisors are actually doing their jobs and the necessary sanctions given to defaulters. Supervisors should have the best interest of student teachers at heart and try to carry out their duties appropriately. During clinical supervision, they should guide student teachers during planning. They should plan with them and be available for any questions. In the same light, student teachers should be creative and willing to learn from their supervisors so that they can grow professionally. They should have respect for their supervisors and avoid any form of conflict. Most importantly, they should attend refresher courses to get enlightened.

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